

INFLUENCE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE ON CHILDREN OF PRIMARY SCHOOL AGE

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the impact of physical education on the body of children of primary school age. In this paper, the importance of physical education and health measures, the forms of such activities, the volumes of various types of physical activity for primary school children and its importance in the functionality of the child's organs are examined in detail.*

Keywords: *physical culture; physical education; training; exercise; sport; activity.*

ВЛИЯНИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ НА ДЕТЕЙ МЛАДШЕГО ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируется влияние занятий физической культурой на организм детей младшего школьного возраста. В данной работе подробно рассмотрено значение физкультурно-оздоровительных мероприятий, формы такой деятельности, объемы различных видов двигательной активности для младших школьников и ее значение в функционировании органов ребенка.*

Ключевые слова: *физическая культура; физическая культура; подготовка; упражнение; спорт; Мероприятия*

INTRODUCTION

In our time, the vital activity of many younger schoolchildren, especially those who live in the city, proceeds in conditions of reduced physical activity. The result of this is an increase in the number of students with various deviations not only in health, but also in physical development. Some have muscle weakness, impaired posture, curvature of the spine, while others have a lag in the development of cardiovascular systems. One of the most realistic ways to support students in these conditions is through intense physical education. Physical development forms motor skills and qualities such as speed, flexibility, strength and stamina, and also fosters a child's determination, confidence, and perseverance.

The actuality of this topic is that the problems of physical education in recent years more and more attract the interest of the pedagogical and medical community, as well as parents. And this is not at all accidental. It is known that properly organized physical education is of great importance for strengthening the health of children, harmonious sports development, increasing the ability to work of their body and expanding multifunctional abilities. In particular, it is very important in 7-10 years. The creation of differentiated physical development is not an easy and painstaking process, requiring, first of all, the accumulation of enormous theoretical material and a substantial enrichment of our knowledge about the characteristics of the growth and formation of the body of children, adolescents and youths. In order to improve each student, it is necessary

to constantly monitor the lessons of sports training, physical development, health and create certain recommendations on how to improve physical education.

The aim of the article: to determine the importance of physical education for children of elementary grades.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Modern society strives to ensure that every child, starting from a very young age, grows up healthy, strong, strong and harmoniously developed. Physical culture is a major factor in improving a person, strengthening his health.

The basis of physical culture is movement, the motor process, sports training, physical exercise. Under the influence of various exercises, the state of health is strengthened, physical development is improved, motor skills are formed, physical qualities are developed and conditions are created in order to realize intellectual, moral, aesthetic and labor education.

RESULTS

Physical education is such a kind of education, the content of which reflects the training in physical exercises, the development of physical qualities, the development of special physical knowledge and the formation of the conscious need for familiarization with sports. In physical education of students, the main role belongs to basic gymnastics, the procedures of which make up a large part of the school curriculum in physical education. The essence of the exercises provides the general physical formation of students and the formation of relevant skills for work and life (moving in the appropriate direction, controlling the movements of the arms, legs, body, head, working poses). All kinds of exercises are designed for strength, endurance, speed.

DISCUSSION

Sports and recreational activities activate the motor mode during the school day, support children of primary school age in tone during mental activity, have a beneficial effect on the body.

Forms of such classes:

1. Early exercise - has a great impact on increasing work capacity, improves health status.
2. Physical exercises in the classroom - remove fatigue, increase intellectual activity, and are carried out when fatigue occurs.
3. Games and exercise during breaks - a useful means of intense relaxation, better health and a return to the learning process. In order to comfortably perform games and physical exercises during breaks, you must first arrange a place, the necessary equipment. As a rule, younger students participate in similar classes of their own free will and express great interest in such events.
4. Daily physical education classes in extended groups solve the following problems:
 - health promotion;
 - hardening of the body;
 - improvement of physical and mental disability;
 - improvement of physical skills;
 - education of the habit of practicing on an ongoing basis and without the help of others.

In extended groups, physical education classes take place in a freer form than physical education lessons can be conducted in the fresh air. The lesson consists of 3 parts:

- preliminary (warm-up, warming up muscles);
- main (sports games, cross, etc.);

- final (training to restore breathing, low-intensity exercises).
- 5. Extracurricular forms of organization of classes. The main form of extracurricular activities in physical education and sports outside school hours are:
 - circles of physical education;
 - sections of general physical training and "Ready for work and defense";

CONCLUSIONS

Physical education did have a beneficial effect on the psyche. Increased blood circulation and deeper breathing contribute to the best supply of blood and oxygen to the brain. Also increases the student's ability to concentrate. Movement over time removes nervous tension. Because of this, there is pleasure: nothing hurts, there are no ailments, all organs function in accordance with the norm. This feeling of joy, in turn, creates a good mood .

At the end of the article, we came to the conclusion that:

- 1) Stable physical culture classes contribute to the healing of the child, strengthen their nervous, cardiovascular and respiratory systems, significantly expand the capabilities of the musculoskeletal system;
- 2) Physical education is the key to healthy well-being, development and growth of the child.

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